

GLOBAL COTTON MARKET AND TRENDS.

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Introduction. As a global industry, the conditions under which cotton is grown and the issues associated with its cultivation vary enormously due to differing environmental, agroecological, climatic, socioeconomic and political conditions. These varying conditions mean that the cultivation of the same crop may result in significantly

different practices and impacts, and that there are significantly different options and capabilities available to address these impacts. An assessment of the impacts of cotton growing, and development of the best options for managing impacts, should therefore always be done with reference to the specific context. However, despite these highly variable conditions, and the site-specific nature of appropriate responses, the impacts of cotton growing are often considered globally. Both the cotton industry and cotton as a raw material are assessed either generically, or on the basis of the averaging of information from different countries without reference to the specific production locations. Access to comprehensive, site-specific, robust and uniform data is necessary to ensure that this “globalization” of the impacts of cotton farming portrays the actual impacts as accurately as possible. One of the responses to the impacts of cotton production has been the establishment of programmes or initiatives working with farmers to improve the sustainability of growing cotton. Development programmes promoting sustainable intensification of agriculture to jointly protect and enhance the livelihoods of producers and the environment have long been working in cotton. There has also been an increasing regulatory interest in resource management by agricultural producers, leading to the implementation of production risk management systems focused on responsible natural resource stewardship. In recent years, there has

been an emergence of initiatives aimed at promoting sustainability in cotton production that involve the downstream supply chain for cotton. This is evident with large retailers who have a growing interest in improving their own overall footprint and who seek to provide customers with greater confidence in the integrity of their products. As a result, there are an increasing number of production standards and systems that claim to promote the objectives of sustainable farming. While these developments are positive, there is a need to understand their relevance to the cotton industry as a whole, including cotton farmers. A consequence of the increase in market-based initiatives to address the impacts of cotton growing is that a wider range of perspectives are influencing the development of these sustainability initiatives, including the approaches to information needs, collection and reporting. It is essential that the interests of all the participants in the cotton supply chain are considered. The specific information requirements of the different participants in the cotton industry will vary depending on how the information is used, and on the value of the information that is collected. This is especially so when it comes to the question of “how the sustainability of cotton farming is assessed”. Among other things, collecting and reporting data requires a clear purpose, as well as clear links between the costs involved in collecting the data and the benefits of doing so. Measuring Sustainability in Cotton Farming Systems – Towards a Guidance Framework (“Cotton Report”) was conceived as a means to bring together the work of programmes and initiatives seeking to reduce the possible negative impacts of cultivating cotton. The objective of the Cotton Report is to recommend a set of indicators to evaluate and track the performance of cotton production across a comprehensive range of sustainability issues. It is addressed to anybody working with cotton farmers – governments, industry organizations, development agencies, ginners, marketers, farmers’ associations, funders and voluntary standards initiatives. The list of recommended indicators was drawn from a range of sustainability programmes with relevance to cotton, an extensive literature review and thematic

expert consultation. The indicator list has been developed on the understanding that any coordinated, industry-wide effort on measuring the sustainability of cotton farming will start with a discussion involving all stakeholders to agree on what are the key issues that need to be addressed, what are the best indicators to assess progress towards becoming more sustainable, and who are the appropriate stakeholders to undertake the responsibility for doing so.

Discussing and agreeing on what indicators or measures should be used to assess at a global level the sustainability of cotton farming will give rise to a range of potential benefits for the cotton industry, including:

- provision of a forum for the global cotton industry to discuss, debate and reach agreement on the priorities for measuring the sustainability performance of the cotton industry;
- better understanding of current levels of “performance” – environmental, economic and social – essential in order to improve performance, as actions can target the most critical areas requiring improvement;
- increased global relevance, comprehension and efficiency of data collection and reporting;
- improved capacity to satisfy market demand: the expectations of retailers and consumers are changing and they have increasingly high expectations both about how products are produced with respect to their environmental and social impact, and – importantly – about access to that information;
- access by the cotton industry to data used by the downstream supply chain to "assess" performance and, therefore, the possibility to check that the data are accurate and representative of cotton performance globally.

The list of recommended indicators is a starting point for discussion among cotton sector stakeholders, so that areas of agreement on these key issues can be found. It needs to be stressed that while there are sustainability issues with a recognized global relevance for which uniform indicators can be used (for instance no child labour involvement), there are also several other sustainability issues which, due

to the diversity and variability in cotton production across regions, are very localized. This report concentrates on the farm and farmer level. Issues relating to downstream activities may arise, but are not covered in any detail. It should also be noted that many of the issues highlighted are relevant to agricultural production in general, not just cotton. Finally, the list is not intended to establish a set of “pass/fail” levels; the focus is on tracking continuous improvement, using agreed measures. Likewise, the rating is designed neither to judge the merits of each sustainability framework or initiative reviewed, nor to identify a preferred system. While an element of commonality around how different programmes and initiatives report on their outcomes is considered desirable, it is recognized that they are working in different countries on a range of issues.

The cotton value chain begins with the farmer, who grows cotton and harvests “seed cotton” from the bolls of the cotton plant. Cotton production systems vary globally, ranging from labour-intensive systems in Africa and Asia to highly mechanized systems in Australia, Brazil and the United States. By weight, seed cotton is composed of roughly one-third cotton lint and two-thirds cottonseed. The cotton lint is separated from the cottonseed (“ginning”) using a cotton gin. Cotton lint is then sold to spinners who produce yarn. Textile manufacturers transform yarns into fabric by knitting or weaving the yarns and applying dyes and finishes. In the final stage, end products (garments, home textiles etc.) are made from fabrics. Cotton and cotton textile industries are central to the economic growth of both developed and developing countries. The large area under cotton cultivation makes it one of the most significant crops in terms of land use after food grains and soybeans. More than 100 million family units are directly engaged in cotton production. When family labour, hired on-farm labour and workers in ancillary services such as transportation, ginning, baling and storage are considered, over 250 million people are involved in the cotton sector. Cotton also provides additional employment to several million people in related industries such as agricultural inputs, machinery and equipment production, cottonseed crushing and textile manufacturing. Cotton has

played an important role in industrial development since the eighteenth century and continues to play a central role today in the developing world as a major source of revenue. The value of the 25.6 million tonnes of cotton production in 2013/14 (**Figure 2**) sold at an average price of about USD 0.91 per pound of lint (USD 2.01/kg), amounts to about USD 51.4 billion.

1-Figure Schematic representation of the cotton textiles value chain

The length of the value chain and the manufacturing costs at the industrial stage result in the total value added throughout the cotton chain (from farm to retail) being several times the value of cotton at the production stage. Increases in cotton yields, the phasing out of textile quotas under the Multifibre Arrangement, and sustained world economic growth fuelled a period of rapid growth for the world cotton market between 2000 and 2005. In the second half of the decade, stagnant cotton yields and the Great Recession resulted in a reduction of the world cotton market. However, substantial distortions caused by government support programmes to cotton farmers and the loss of price competitiveness in the face of competing textile fibres (mainly polyester) in the 2010s created a wedge between increasing cotton production and declining demand for cotton. The accumulated gap between world cotton production and world cotton consumption between 2010/11 and 2013/14 amounted to 11.6 million tonnes. Most of the additional carrying stocks were absorbed by the

China National Cotton Reserves Corporation (CNCRC) as part of its efforts to maintain domestic farm prices. In 2013/14, China and India accounted for 51% of world cotton mill use (**Figure 3**). Pakistan, Turkey, Brazil, Bangladesh and the United States accounted for an additional 25%. While cotton is mostly processed in developing countries, per capita consumption of cotton at retail level is highest in developed countries. About one-third of world cotton production is traded internationally. In terms of export value, cotton is one of the world's most important agricultural commodities with a market size of USD 17.4 billion in 2013/14, with the United States and India accounting for half of world cotton exports, and Australia, Brazil, Francophone Africa and Uzbekistan accounting for an additional 32% (**Figure 3**).

2-Figure Cotton lint production and consumption (thousand tonnes) by country.

3-Figure

Cotton lint import and export (thousand tonnes) by country (2013/14)

In a year characterized by strong government interventions through the CNCRC, China accounted for 55% of world cotton imports in 2011/12. In 2013/14, Chinese imports accounted for 35% of world trade, while Bangladesh, Viet Nam, Indonesia Turkey and Pakistan jointly accounted for an additional 37%. Between 2003/04 and 2010/11, China's share of world cotton imports averaged 29% (**Figure 3**).

SUMMARY

Trade is expected to continue growing over the next few decades (as in the past six decades) with its share of world cotton production and mill use remaining around one-third. However, the origin and destination of cotton trade will likely experience variations over time, as cotton mill use continues to migrate to regions with the lowest costs of yarn production.

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